

NOTES

Substitution of Strontium and Barium in the Bone Mineral

(Mrs.) REKHA DAS and BALARAM NANDA

Post-Graduate Department of Zoology
and

PREMA N. PATEL*

Post-Graduate Department of Chemistry,
G.M. College, Sambalpur-768 004

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BONE is a dense, hard and highly specialised tissue, composed of organic, inorganic and aqueous fractions. A tough fibrous protein network called collagen, hexoses in the form of a semifluid cement substance and cells constitute the organic matrix while the inorganic part is composed primarily of crystalline hydroxylapatite amounting to about 40% by weight. Calcium hydroxylapatite (CaHA), $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$ is the primary crystalline inorganic component of human skeletal system^{1,2}. It is isomorphous with the naturally occurring mineral, fluorapatite (Fap), $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6\text{F}_2$. It undergoes a series of cationic and anionic exchange reactions which are of biological and physico-chemical significance. The $\text{OH}^- \rightarrow \text{F}^-$ substitution functions as the basis for the prophylactic action of fluorine in the prevention of dental carries. Environmental pollution due to some poisonous divalent cations is increasing in recent times. The divalent cations from the environments get incorporated into the human skeletal system leading to poisoning and consequent metabolic effect.

Calcium hydroxylapatite (CaHA) can be prepared from aqueous media^{3,4}. The ionic radii⁵ of calcium (0.99Å), strontium (1.13Å) and barium (1.35Å) are close enough to form solid solutions between isomorphous substances containing these ions. Apatite undergoes a series of cationic and anionic replacement reactions⁶. The $\text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Sr}^{2+}$ and/or Ba^{2+} replacement reactions in CaHA are of biological significance. They form the basis of incorporation of Sr^{2+} and Ba^{2+} into human skeletal system keeping one of them constant according to the following equation.

Solid solutions of calcium, strontium and barium hydroxylapatites keeping one of them constant were

prepared separately earlier by firing mixtures containing various proportions of calcium, strontium and barium hydroxylapatite at about 1300°. These samples prepared by solid state reaction were however found to be discontinuous and non-homogeneous.

Now an attempt has been made to develop a new method of preparation of the homogeneous solid solutions of mixed calcium-strontium-barium hydroxylapatite over the entire compositional range by the method of coprecipitation⁸⁻¹⁰.

Experimental

All chemicals used in this study were either A. R. (B.D.H.) or E. P. (E. Merck) grade. Water used in the preparation and in washing was boiled to remove CO_2 and used immediately.

Stoichiometric quantities of ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (solution A) and a solution containing Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} and Ba^{2+} ions in the proportion desired for the solid solution (solution B) were prepared separately in CO_2 free, double-distilled water. The pH of the solutions was maintained above 11 by the addition of excess of liquor ammonia. A part of the solution B was taken in a flask (2 L) fitted with two separating funnels and a delivery tube. Solution A and solution B were mixed individually in the separating funnels and added dropwise to the flask simultaneously. Precipitation was carried out in CO_2 free atmosphere and the precipitation medium was well stirred by bubbling CO_2 free air to prevent the formation of carbonate-apatites.

The precipitate and mother liquor were refluxed for 30 min to improve the homogeneity and crystallinity. Maintenance of exact pH was essential for the preparation¹¹. The precipitate was washed thoroughly with distilled water to free it from ammonium salts. Samples dried at 100° for a few hr were analysed colorimetrically¹² and their molar volume determined by density method using toluene¹³ as solvent.

X-ray diffraction techniques :

The X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples were obtained with Siemens Powder diffractometer with NaCl (TL counter employing CuK_α) (nickel filtered) radiation with a scanning speed of 1 degree (2θ) per min. Samples dried at 110° for a few hr were used for the purpose.

Lattice constant measurements :

CaHA, SrHA and BaHA are hexagonal. The a_0 and c_0 were determined^{14,15} for all the samples by measuring the diffraction angle, 2θ, of the

* Author for correspondence.

three planes, (312), (213) and (321). Each sample was thoroughly mixed with 25% NaCl which served as a standard, so that the observed values of $\sin \theta$ for the solid solution lines could be corrected directly for absorption and instrumental errors. The lattice constant of NaCl at 26° was taken to be 5.64034 Å¹⁶. A least squares calculation on the corrected values of $\sin \theta$ for the three reflections then gave the two parameters, a_0 and c_0 , for each sample. The average probable error in unit cell parameters is less than ± 0.05 Å.

Results and Discussion

The observed value of molar g-atom ratio of $\frac{Ca}{P}$, $\frac{Sr}{P}$, $\frac{Ba}{P}$ for the end members and $\frac{Ca+Sr+Ba}{P}$ were found to be equal to 1.664 (theoretical 1.67) and is consistent with the formation of homogeneous solid solution¹³. This was further supported by the closeness of the values of molar volumes of the end members and those of the intermediate samples which lie within the range of end members.

The formation of solid solutions can be further confirmed by X-ray diffraction analysis. Apatites crystallize in a hexagonal structure with space group $P6_3/m$ ^{17,18}. Lattice parameters showed increase of c/a ratio consequent upon the introduction of bigger ions, $[Sr^{2+} (1.13 \text{ Å}) \text{ and } Ba^{2+} (1.35 \text{ Å})]$, in place of $Ca^{2+} (0.99 \text{ Å})$ in the apatite lattice. Such dilation with the proportion of Ca-Sr-BaHA was evident as the unit cell volume of the samples calculated on the basis of the experimentally determined lattice constant increased with the proportion of strontium and barium in Ca-Sr-BaHA.

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Synthesis and Structural Studies of β -Mercapto Ethyl(2-Hydroxy-5-Methyl Phenyl)-Benzalimine and β -Mercapto Ethyl Anil of 1-(2',4'-Dihydroxy Phenyl)Pentane Complexes of Pd(II)

V. K. RASTOGI*, A. K. KATIYAR†, R. C. SAXENA†
and
A. K. KOTNALA†

Molecular Spectroscopy Research Laboratory,
Department of Physics, Meerut College, Meerut-250 001

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IN view of the reported anticancer activity of platinum metals we describe the preparation and characterisation of some complexes of Pd(II) with the Schiff bases derived from 2-hydroxy-5-methyl benzophenone, 2,4-dihydroxy valerophenone and β -mercapto ethylamine hydrochloride. The compounds have been characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic measurements, ir and electronic spectral data and a square planar structure has been assigned to them.

Experimental

$[Pd(C_{10}H_{15}NSO)_2H_2O]$: Palladium Schiff base complex was synthesized by adding a calculated amount (2.134 g; 10 m mole) of palladium chloride to an ethanolic solution of β -mercapto ethyl(2-hydroxy-5-methyl phenyl)benzalimine (3.07 g; 10 m mole) in equimolar ratio 1 : 1 (M : L). The orange coloured precipitate thus formed was filtered, washed with ethanol and finally with ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

$[Pd(C_{13}H_{17}NSO_2)H_2O].3H_2O$: An equimolar mixture of palladium chloride (2.134 g; 10 m mole) and β -mercapto ethyl anil of 1-(2',4'-dihydroxy phenyl)pentane (2.895 g; 10 m mole) in ethanol was refluxed on a water bath for ~2 hr. An orange coloured complex was obtained which was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator over fused calcium chloride.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are orange in colour and insoluble in water. Analytical data of the complexes suggest 1 : 1 (M : L) stoichiometry. Magnetic measurements indicate that both the complexes are diamagnetic at room temperature, suggesting a D_{4h} symmetry around the central metal ion as expected for a d^8 configuration.

The electronic spectra of both the complexes show three bands in the regions 16000-20000, 23500-29000 and 29000-33000 cm^{-1} which are assigned to the

* On leave from Lajpat Rai College, Sahibabad-201 005.

† Department of Chemistry, M. M. College, Modinagar-201 204.